

EDUCATION FOR VALUE DEVELOPMENT & IT'S SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

Human beings reside & retain in the society. Values help them to exist, survive & sustain in the in society. Values mean an individual keeps it in mind which involves respect, love, appreciation, affection, care and many other things towards other person. Building values is an integral part in the process of internalization of values because an individual can only give what one has within (Reimers and Chung, 2019). Educational Institutions may be considered as important place, where students spend their time and learn many more thing. Values have relations with human life. Value means 'worth whileness of a thing'. Values are expressed by opinions or behaviour of a particular individuals. But in today's society it is seen that values are gradually detoriating . For this society suffering so many ill events. There is an erosion of values in social, moral, cultural i.e at all levels. Due to which numbers of problems arises in our society like murder, corruption, cheating, and violence of women and children right. After introduction of value-based education in schools, there will be development of stable and solid learning environment and academic achievement will be enhanced along with infusing social and other related skills which help them to always grow. The teacher plays an important role in inculcating values among students. They always keep on guiding them and show the right path. There are different modes and methods by which the values can be imbibed among the students in the present education system. Therefore, this study is conducted to find out the importance of values in life & the ways by which value can be imbibed in the students' mind for it's use & sustainability. This article will be beneficial for students, teachers, parents etc.

Keywords: Education, Values, Teacher, Student, Educational Institutions, sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Science and technology has acquired a crucial role in life of human beings , it has created some problems also in 4people's live residing in the society. Due to advanced technical

era, human minds have become fully mechanical. People understand the language of profit and loss only which has made them materialistic entities. The societal norms, the values of life have been disappeared from our lives. A value means worthwhile ness of a thing. It was expressed by our ideas, thinking process, behaviour etc. Value education enshrined in every aspects of Indian culture. Yet it is a matter of great concern that gradually we are losing our values with the view that we tend to become cornet and hypocrite. Even our current educational system is oriented towards giving knowledge and skills that would make students saleable products and nothing else. This education system has developed only cognitive aspect of a man and left effective and psychomotor aspects starving, which results in sordid rapes, heinous murders, treacheries, chicaneries, frauds and malpractices. Value based education will include the development of humanistic, ethical, Constitutional, and universal human values (NEP, 2020). Such a system of education is devoid of the primary human values of solidarity, justice, equality, brotherhood, affection, generosity, empathy etc.

Thus the problem of value crises seems inherent in the system of education itself. Students are the future citizen & backbone of India. The future of the country depends on the values imparted to them during their life as student. Moral lessons are be properly implemented among the students in schools and colleges. Students have immense power of observation and their feelings/emotions are deep rooted. Values in higher education make one's own life and the life of his fellow beings lively and meaningful& peaceful.

Character oriented education that focuses basic values and ethnic values in one's psyche is known as 'Value Based Education'. The subject that foster to understand 'what is valuable' for human happiness is called value education. Value education is to help everyone in improving the value system that he/she holds and puts it to use in daily life. Once, one has understood & realise his/ her values in life he/she can evaluate and control the various choices he/she makes in his/her life. Value education enable to understand the needs deeply and internalize goals correctly and helps to remove confusions, misunderstanding and contradictions and bring balance at all levels. It also helps to remove confusions and contradictions and enables to rightly utilize the technological innovations. Values form the bases of all thoughts, 3 behaviours and actions. Once we know what is valuable to us, these values become the foundations, the anchor for our actions. We also require to understand the universality of various human values, because then only we can have a definite and common program for education on values . After that we can assure of a happy, peaceful, and harmonious human society.

Need of the Study

Value education is the process by which people are instructed to give values to others. Value education imparted by the teacher plays crucial role to shape students' life. Teacher can teach them that it is far more honourable to fail than to cheat. Honesty, truthfulness, trust, belief, respect, affection these words has no room to occupy in their (young children) minds and hearts. Everywhere there is violence, selfishness, crimes and criminals. Social environment of the society is suffering due to this value crisis. The education system of the country is cause for this. It is unable to provide employment to the young generation after they pass from higher studies institutions. And this failure creates restlessness among the youth which ultimately gives call to do something vital for the society. Today, in this crucial situation, need of value education has become very high. Because it is the value education which only gives knowledge among the youth about tolerance, stability, peace to deal with any situation comes before them. Knowledge of spiritual education, moral education, social values all are included in Value Education. So this paper tried to study about need of value education among students. Because students are backbone of a country.

Value Education-It's Types

Cultural

Cultural values focus on what is right and wrong, good and evil behaviour. Language, ethics, social hierarchy, aesthetics, education, law, economics, philosophy, and many social Institutions all fosters cultural values.

Moral

Ethical principles focus on respecting others' and one's own authority, keeping commitments, avoid unnecessary conflicts with others, avoiding cheating and dishonesty, praising people and making them work, and encouraging others.

Personal

Personal values reflects whatever a person needs in social interaction. Personal values covers beauty, morality, confidence, self-motivation, regularity, ambition, courage, vision, imagination, and so on.

Spiritual

Spirituality is the greatest moral value. Purity, meditation, yoga, discipline, control, clarity, and devotion to God are burning examples of spiritual virtues. Spiritual value education explains self-discipline concepts. Satisfaction along with self-discipline, absence of wants, general greed, and freedom from seriousness.

Social

A person cannot survive in the world unless they communicate with others. People are searching for social values viz. love, affection, friendship, noble groups, reference groups, impurity, hospitality, courage, service, justice, freedom, patience, forgiveness, coordination, compassion, tolerance, and so on.

Universal

We identify ourselves with the mankind and the universe by including universal ideals. Life, joy, fraternity, love, sympathy, service, paradise, truth, and eternity are universal values.

Educational values

Values education covers various topics related to citizenship and ethics, viz:

Empathy

By putting ourselves in other people's shoes both cognitively and emotionally, we can enhance our ability to resolve conflicts and understand others' opinions.

Equal opportunities

The principle which ensures we all are equal is one of the pillars of democracy, and also it fosters social inclusion and community life.

Respect for Environment

Value education makes us aware of the consequences of our actions on the planet and inculcate in us a respect for nature.

Health Care

We can minimise the health risks/issues by encouraging the right attitudes and tackling health education from a dynamic, personal and collective point of views.

Critical Thinking

This right way of thinking makes us more analytical and observant, teaches us to recognise quality information and helps us to solve problems accordingly.

Value Education & its importance

Value education need to be integrated into the educational process instead of being considered a separate academic field. The value of value education may be understood from many perspectives. Value education is most important in the modern world because

1. It enhances decision-making skills.
2. It inculcates important values in students, such as kindness, compassion, and empathy etc.
3. Children's curiosity is ignited, their values and interests are developed, and this further supplement students' skill development.

4. It enhances a feeling of brotherhood and patriotism, which helps students in accepting of all cultures and religions.
5. If the students are taught about the proper values and ethics, it gives students' lives a positive direction.
6. It supplements students in discovering their true calling in life—one that involves giving back to society and striving to improve themselves.
7. A mature responsibility come with getting older. Occasionally, this can create a sense of meaninglessness, which increases the risk of mental health disorders, midlife crises, and growing dissatisfaction with one's own life. Value education needs to fill a void in peoples' lives in some small way.
8. People are more convinced and dedicated to their goals and passions when they learn about values & it's importance in the society and in their own lives. **1** This causes awareness, which then produces deliberate , meaningful and fruitful decisions.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out importance of Education for value development of students.
- To identify strategies to impart value education among students &it's sustainability.

Methodologies

This is descriptive survey. This paper is theoretical.

Analysis and interpretation

Objectives No-1.

- To find out importance of Education for value development of students.
- To ensure child's holistic development.
- To enhance the attitudes towards balance lifestyle.
- To increase awareness about national history of our rich cultural heritage, constitutional rights, national integration, development in community and environment.
- To develop awareness about the values and their significance along with role.
- To develop character in human personality with purity in consciousness, peace in mind and life prosperity.
- To develop holistic personality and bring divinity in society.
- To re-establish, through education and research, a society based on spiritual, moral and human values.
- To remove ignorance, superstition, and social evils through spiritual education.

- To raise awareness through education and counselling about the adverse effects of alcohol, drugs and tobacco.
- To inspire students to develop their personality, responsibility and social values based on human values.
- To inculcate dynamic spirituality among students that they could withstand the suicidal tendencies aroused on account of frustration and tension.
- To motivate students to be free from bad habits, addictions and blind faith and become the true and ideal support to their family and society.
- To establish harmony in relationships at family level and social level, that we can create a one world family.
- To ensure and sustain the true art of living to lead a lotus-like life and have a balance of work and pleasure.

Objectives No-2

To identify strategies to impart value education among students & it's sustainability.

- The personality of the teacher should be such which reflects morality in his behaviour.
- The teacher act as the role model in a student's life. So the teacher should be cautious about his presentation before his students.
- He should have a keen observation upon his students' behaviour also. And if he finds any wrong deed from them, he should handle the situation intelligently so that students do not misguide.
- Honesty and truthfulness in colleges are effective than moral preaching.
- They quickly copy their teachers. The teachers must behave properly and set an example. The students look at them as their ideal one. Even some students of cultured and refined families lose moral values & ethical values, if the environment of school is not proper.
- If a child observes that his teacher is truthful and honest, he will also imbibe some of the virtues.
- Teachers are ideal & inspiration for students. The relationship among students and teachers are very strong.
- The moral education should be taught at educational institutions. Our curriculum should include the study of life biographies of great personalities who followed the right path in their life.

- Teachers play a pivotal role in the education and student's life. A person with proper vision, experience and an education degree can enter the teaching profession. Teaching job has a great responsibility than a mere job. It has influences on the growth and well-being of the nation. For that, teachers should be provided with the knowledge of proper in service and pre service teacher training.
- The curriculum of teacher training programme should include courses on value education. When teachers will be well equipped with the knowledge of value education knowledge to their students also. They will be aware about the causes of value crisis and can deal with adequately.
- Teachers must have the up-to-date knowledge with the current times so that they can be able to understand their students' psychology. To prepare the students of college level, it is very important that the teachers should be multi-dimensional and update.
- Proper teacher training programme is essential before the teacher enters into the field of teaching.
- In addition to the school or college home plays a vital role to inculcate value education for their child. From the very early age value education should be provided by the parents. Parents should teach them how to respect elders & also orient them about ethics, morality, humanity, honesty etc.

Findings

- Values are mostly need for the college students. If the students gain the spiritual knowledge even if slightly, they can understand that materialistic world has no importance in their life. Ultimate goal of life and education is Moksha. This sense of spirituality is the only solution at this time to remove value crisis from the society which leads to sustainable value development.
- Study reveals that after family, school or college is fully responsible to ensure value education among the students and teacher is the facilitator of value education among the students. Because teachers foster knowledge about ethics, values etc.
- It was found that if a school/college cannot give value education to the students, education can never be a complete process. If a student don't know how to show honour to their teachers, to the bus driver, to the chowkider, or to the waiter boy of a hotel that education system is meaningless. So teacher's prime duty is to enable students to learn how to respect different people accordingly which is sustainable value development.

- Without values students are make literate but not educated. To become a good educator in real sense we must need value education. Teacher must give moral education to the students as morals and human values are the basic foundations for the future of any individual.
- Teacher should teach the each student that for every enemy there is a friend. Also teach them to it is far more honourable to fail than to cheat. Teach them to learn how to enjoy winning when he does win and also learn them if they earned 100 rupees is far more value than a thousand found in easily etc.
- Teacher provides the student with moral values like importance of truth, regard, trust etc which will help them in their further future in both personal and professional life that focuses on sustainable value development.
- Knowledge of social values help students to become strong enough, when they will enter into the professional life. They will be well adjusted in any situation. Social values will teach them sense of responsibility, cooperativeness, healthy competition, adjustment, respect etc.
- Teachers can provide students about the knowledge of Puran, Upanishads, Epics like Ramayana etc where students will find the love and respect for the adults, affection and give up for the young, love for the motherland etc. which will change their mind. They will become human rather than just a robot that ensures sustainable value development.
- Teacher is the inspiration for the students, especially for the college students. Teachers' activity & behaviour is followed by the students. Behaviour of the teachers reflect in the behaviour of the students.
- If teacher is boosted with the knowledge of value education he/she can easily create a positive environment for the students where they can grow with positive vibes & establish the same around them giving importance which leads to sustainable value development.

Suggestions

- Value education should be introduced as a compulsory subject at college level along with school level & importance should be given on it's sustainability.
- Teacher should hold the responsibility because teacher is the inspiration for all the students, especially for the college students. Teachers' activities & behaviour is followed by the students as he /she is the model of all the students.
- If the teacher is well equipped with the knowledge on value education, he/she can easily ensure a positive environment for the students, where they can grow with positive human values. Family plays a significant role from the very early ages they should take required action

for formation of a good character with honesty & provide education for sustainable value development.

Conclusion

Students are the future of a nation. So to become a good students they should possess high moral values. Moral lessons should be properly implemented among students in schools and colleges. Family must imbibe human values among students along with the teacher. Because teacher is the one, whom student like most with their parents. One word of the teacher is accepted easily by the children than their parents' hundred words. They can bring changes in their life. Students always follow a teacher. Teacher is inspiration for student. Value education is most essential for students' life. Because value education is the basic need which decide what is correct or wrong of their life. Education for value development ensures social, moral, integrity, character, spirituality etc. It encourages the quality of humanity, strength honesty of child. They become responsible citizen of country. People with high ethical values cannot do any anti-social activities leading to sustainable value development.

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